

CHEGARAVIY MASALALARNI AMALIY DASTURLAR PAKETI YORDAMIDA INTEGRALLASH VA DASTURIY TA'MINOTINI YARATISH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Maple kompyuter matematikasi tizimidan "Bir necha o'zgaruvchilar funksiyalarining integral hisobi" mavzusini o'rganishda qanday foydalanish mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan. Keltirilgan misollarda, karrali integralni hisoblash usullari tasvirlangan va ushbu materialning amaliy mohiyati ochib berilgan.

"Bir necha o'zgaruvchilar funksiyalarining integral hisobi" mavzusi oliy o'quv yurtlari o'quv jarayonida muhim o'rin egallaydi. U matematikaning o'zida ham katta ahamiyatga ega va amaliy masalalarni yechishda keng qo'llaniladi. Shu bilan birga, o'rganilayotgan amaliy masalalarning matematik modellashtirish jarayonini yanada ko'rgazmaliroq va tushunarli bo'lishi uchun kompyuter matematikasi tizimlarining har xil paketlaridan, xususan Maple tizimidan foydalanish mumkin.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Maple kompyuter matematikasi tizimining bir necha integrallarni hisoblash va amaliy masalalarni yechish imkoniyatlarini ko'rib chiqish.

Tadqiqot ob'yekti. Karrali integrallarni hisoblash yoki ularni geometriyada qo'llashga oid masalalarni yechish va bu masalalarni yechishdagi Maple

$$\iiint_{(V)} (xz)^2 dx dy dz,$$

bu yerda, V hajmli jism $x = 2$, $y = 2x$, $y = 0$, $z = 0$, $z = xy$ sirtlar bilan chegaralangan.

Yechish. Uch o'lchamli fazoviy chizmalarni qo'lda bajarish juda qiyin bo'lgani sababli, biz berilgan jismning yaqqol tasvirni yaratish uchun kompyuterdan foydalanamiz.

>restart;

>with(plots):

>with(student):

>A1:=plot3d([(2),(u),(v)],u=0..4,v=0..2*u,axes=normal):

A2:=plot3d([(u),(2*u),(v)],u=0..2,v=0..(u^2)*2,axes=normal):

A3:=plot3d([(u),(0),(v)],u=0..2,v=0..0,axes=normal):

A4:=plot3d([(u),(v),(0)],u=0..2,v=0..2*u,axes=normal):

A5:=plot3d([(u),(v),(u*v)],u=0..2,v=0..2*u,axes=normal):

>display({A1,A2,A3,A4, A5},labels=[x,y,z],scaling=constrained);

Berilgan integralni hisoblaymiz

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_{(V)} (xz)^2 dx dy dz &= \int_0^2 dx \int_0^{2x} dy \int_0^{xy} (xz)^2 = \\ &= \int_0^2 dx \int_0^{2x} x^2 \left(\frac{y^4}{4} \Big|_0^{xy} \right) dy = \frac{1}{3} \int_0^2 x^5 dx \int_0^{2x} y^3 dy = \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \int_0^2 x^5 \left(\frac{y^4}{4} \Big|_0^{2x} \right) dx = \frac{4}{3} \int_0^2 x^9 dx = \frac{4}{3} \frac{x^{10}}{10} \Big|_0^2 = \frac{2048}{15}. \end{aligned}$$

Maple tizimida berilgan integralni hisoblash quyidagicha bajariladi:

> restart:

with(student):

Tripleint((x*z)^2,z=0..x*y,y=0..2*x,

x= (0..2);

> value(%);

$$\int_0^2 \int_0^{2x} \int_0^{xy} x^2 z^2 dz dy dx >$$

$$\frac{2048}{15}$$

2-misol. Yuqoridan $z = 4 - x^2 - y^2$ paraboloid bilan va Oxy tekisligida $x = \pm 1, y = \pm 1$ to‘g‘ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan kvadrat asosga ega bo‘lgan to‘g‘ri brus hajmini hisoblang.

Yechish. Birinchidan, biz Maple tizimi yordamida jism rasmini chizamiz:

>restart:

>with(plots):

>with(student):

>A1:=plot3d([(u),(v),(4-u^2-v^2)],u=-1..1,v=-1..1,axes=normal):

A2:=plot3d([(u),(v),(0)],u=-1..1,v=-1..1,axes=normal):

A3:=plot3d([(1),(u),(v)],u=-1..1,v=0..3-u^2,axes=normal):

A4:=plot3d([(-1),(u),(v)],u=-1..1,v=0..3-u^2,axes=normal):

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A5:=plot3d([(u),(1),(v)],u=-1..1,v=0..3-u^2,axes=normal):  
A6:=plot3d([(u),(-1),(v)],u=-1..1,v=0..3-u^2,axes=normal):  
>display({A1,A2,A3,A4,A5,A6},labels=[x,y,z],scaling=constrained,  
view=[-1.5 ..1.5,-1.5 ..1.5,0 ..4.5]);
```


Brus asosi tamonlari Ox va Oy o'qlariga parallell bo'lgan kvadrat bo'lganligi sababli, ikkala o'zgaruvchilar bo'yicha integrallash chegaralari o'zgarmas kattaliklar bo'ladi.

$$V = \iint_{(V)} f(x, y) dx dy$$

Formuladan foydalanib brus hajmini hisoblaymiz va maple da integralni hisoblash quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \int_{-1}^1 dx \int_{-1}^1 (4 - x^2 - y^2) dy = \int_{-1}^1 \left[4y - x^2 - \frac{y^2}{3} \right]_{-1}^1 dx = \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 \left(8 - 2x^2 - \frac{2}{3} \right) dx = \left[\frac{22}{3}x - \frac{2}{3}x^3 \right]_{-1}^1 = \frac{44}{3} - \frac{4}{3} = 13\frac{1}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

```
>restart:
```

```
with(student):
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```
Doubleint(4-x^2-y^2,y=-1..1,x=-1..1);
```

> value (%);

$$\frac{40}{3} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 4 - x^2 - y^2 dy dx$$

XULOSA

O'quv mashg'ulot jarayonida nafaqat "qo'lda", balki kompyuterda hisoblashlardan foydalanish matematik modellashtirish jarayonini talabalar uchun yanada ko'rgazmaliroq va tushinarliroq bo'lishini ta'minlaydi (ayniqsa, uch o'lchovli ob'yektlar uchun);

Hisoblashlarning murakkabligini kamaytirishga imkoni beradi va bir xil matematik muammoni hal qilish uchun matematik va kompyuter usullarini solishtirish imkonini beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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